

1 **RIPK2 activation in primitive hematopoietic cells.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7
8 The receptor interacting kinases (RIPK1-4) and mixed lineage lymphoid kinase (MLKL) govern bifurcating
9 signal transduction decisions at the single cell level made in bifunctional pathways that control cell death
10 programs and effector function like in cytokine secretion in the immune system. Cell-type and
11 developmental stage-specific functions of each respective RIPK and of MLKL remain poorly understood.
12 We measured total transcription in the cord blood, in immature thymocytes (pro- and pre-T cells, and in
13 single and double negative maturing lymphocytes during T-lymphocyte development at the thymus to
14 discover factors that govern stage-specific switching. We describe here early activation of RIPK2 in the
15 cord blood during human development. An as of yet undefined developmental, isoform-specific function for
16 RIPK2 in the hematopoietic compartment exists.
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28